

Photocatalytic degradation of azo dye by silver-impregnated zinc oxide

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Abstract : The photocatalytic degradation of Congo Red, an azo dye has been investigated in presence of aqueous suspension of ZnO under visible light irradiation. ZnO was impregnated with Ag of varying concentrations such as 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 atom percentage and the samples were calcined at different temperatures for 2 h. The catalyst was characterized by XRD. The photocatalytic activity of ZnO was found to be enhanced by silver impregnation and 1 atom percent of silver-impregnated ZnO has high photocatalytic activity. Calcination of samples at higher temperature decreased the photocatalytic activity. The effect of various process parameters such as catalyst loading, initial concentration of dye and pH of the solution has been investigated. The kinetics of dye degradation was also studied and the data were well fitted to pseudo-first order kinetic model.

Keywords : Photocatalysis, silver impregnated ZnO, Congo Red, dye degradation, surface modification, textile effluent.

Introduction

Synthetic dyes from textile waste water are the major industrial pollutants and water contaminants^{1,2}. It is estimated that 10–15% of dye is lost during the dyeing process and released into effluents³. Conventional physical and chemical processes such as adsorption, precipitation, flocculation, reverse osmosis and ultra filtration can be used for the treatment of textile effluents^{4,5}. However, these methods are nondestructive and create pollutant concentrated phases^{6,7}. Dyes are generally resistant to biological degradation due to the presence of large degree of aromatics⁸. Azo compounds are resistant to aerobic degradation but the azo dye linkage is reduced under anaerobic conditions to aromatic amines that are colourless, toxic and carcinogenic⁹.

Semiconducting material assisted photocatalytic oxidation of organic compounds can be an alternative to conventional methods for the removal of organic pollutants^{10–12}. TiO₂ is one of the most commonly used

photocatalysts for a wide variety of organic dyes. ZnO is another potential photocatalyst due to its absorption over a large fraction of solar spectrum and so it is the most suitable catalyst for photo degradation in the presence of sunlight¹³. Lizama *et al.*¹⁴ reported that ZnO was more effective catalyst than TiO₂ for the degradation of Reactive Blue-19. Daneshvar *et al.*¹⁵ reported ZnO to be a suitable alternative to TiO₂ for the degradation of Acid Red 14.

In the present study the effect of silver impregnation on ZnO for photocatalytic degradation of Congo Red, an azo dye has been investigated under visible light irradiation.

Experimental

Materials :

Zinc oxide and Congo Red were obtained from Merck, India. The chemicals used in the study were of analytical reagent grade. All the solutions were prepared using double distilled water.

Preparation of silver-impregnated ZnO photocatalyst :

Silver-impregnated ZnO containing 1 atom% of silver was prepared by liquid impregnation method^{16,17}. Silver nitrate solution containing 105 mg in 100 mL was added to 5 g of ZnO and the mixture was stirred for 4 h and allowed to stand for 24 h. The water was then evaporated at 100 °C. The dried solid was grounded to fine powder in an agate mortar and calcined at 200, 400 and 600 °C for 2 h in muffle furnace. Silver-impregnated ZnO of 0.5 and 1.5 atom percent were prepared by following similar procedure.

Characterization of catalyst :

The catalysts were characterized for their structure by X-ray diffraction (XRD). The XRD patterns of the powdered samples were recorded by Bruker 8 D advanced X-ray diffractometer.

Photocatalytic studies :

The experimental setup used for the photocatalytic degradation consisted of a 250 mL Borosil beaker with water circulation outside. The beaker was placed on a magnetic stirrer, above which a high pressure mercury vapour lamp (125 W, Philips) emitting visible light was placed. ZnO or Ag-impregnated ZnO at a dose of 1 g L⁻¹ was added to 100 mL of the dye solution in the beaker. The distance of the light source from the upper level of dye solution in the beaker is 18 cm. This is the optimum distance that can be maintained between the dye solution in the beaker and the light source so that all the light from the source falls on the reactor. If the distance is increased, some of the light may fall outside the reactor and maximum intensity will not reach the dye solution. The solution was stirred in the dark for 30 min to establish the adsorption equilibrium. The zero time reading was taken and the solution was then irradiated. Aliquots of 5 mL samples were taken at regular time intervals and centrifuged to analyse the percent degradation of the dye.

Analysis :

The percent degradation of Congo Red was found out spectrophotometrically by measuring absorbance of the dye solution at λ_{\max} 505 nm. The decolourisation efficiency (%) was calculated as

$$\text{Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{C_0 - C}{C_0} \times 100$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration of the dye and C is the concentration of the dye after irradiation. Similar experiments were carried out by varying concentration of dye solution, catalyst loading and pH of the solution.

Results and discussion*Catalyst characterization by XRD analysis :*

The XRD patterns obtained for powdered ZnO and Ag-ZnO of various concentrations of silver impregnation 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 atom% dried at 100 °C are shown in Fig. 1(a) indicating well indexed phases of ZnO wurtzite structure. The intensities of XRD peaks increased with the addition of silver upto 1 atom% indicating better crystallinity of the samples and further addition of silver decreased the intensity. Silver can be incorporated in ZnO system either as a substituent for Zn²⁺ or as an interstitial atom. If the silver is substituted for Zn²⁺, a corresponding peak shift would be expected in the XRD. Absence of such changes in the peak positions indicate that impregnation of ZnO with Ag⁺ ions does not change the crystal structure, may be due to low percent of silver addition and surface deposition. Small extra peak in XRD patterns [Fig. 1(b)] of calcined samples at 200, 400 and 600 °C is the characteristic of metallic silver^{18,19}.

Visible absorption spectra of dye :

Fig. 2 shows absorption spectra of Congo Red during photo irradiation with Ag-ZnO catalyst. Congo Red has a characteristic absorption peak at 505 nm. The rate of decolourisation of dye was recorded with respect to the change in intensity at 505 nm. The absorption peak of the dye was diminished and finally disappeared during reaction, which indicates the degradation of the dye.

Photocatalytic degradation :

The aqueous solutions of Congo Red (7.17×10^{-5} M) were found to degrade up to 50% and 98% on visible light irradiation for 30 min in the presence of ZnO (1 g L⁻¹) and Ag-ZnO (1 g L⁻¹), respectively. The degradation efficiency of Ag-ZnO was found to be higher than ZnO as shown in Fig. 3.

The effect of calcination temperature of Ag-ZnO on degradation of Congo Red was also studied. The percent degradation decreased with increasing calcination temperature. Samples heated at 100 and 200 °C have higher activity than samples calcined at 400 and 600 °C. Higher

Fig. 1. Powder XRD patterns of ZnO and various atom% of Ag-ZnO. (a) Dried at 100 °C and (b) 1 atom% Ag-ZnO calcined at various temperatures.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of dye solution during the course of the reaction.

Fig. 3. Effect of silver-impregnation on degradation of Congo Red. [Congo Red] = $7.17 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Catalyst] = $1.0 g L^{-1}$; (☆) undoped ZnO, (□) 0.5% Ag-ZnO, (○) 1.0% Ag-ZnO, (Δ) 1.5% Ag-ZnO.

temperature calcinations have a negative effect on photocatalytic activity because the presence of silver promotes the densification and grain growth of ZnO at higher temperatures by forming a silver island in the ZnO matrix, which causes the reduction in active surface sites of the photocatalyst for the adsorption of dye and light²⁰. The degradation efficiency also varied with concentration of silver ion impregnation. With increasing silver loading from 0.5 to 1.5 atom percent, the degradation efficiency was found to be maximum for 1 atom percent of silver impregnation of ZnO. This is the optimal concentration of Ag for impregnation of ZnO by this method.

Effect of catalyst loading :

The effect of catalyst loading on dye degradation was studied by varying catalyst concentration from 0.25 to $2.0 g L^{-1}$ for $7.17 \times 10^{-5} M$ dye solution at natural pH of dye solution 6.95. It observed from the Fig. 4(a) that the initial slopes of the curves increases greatly with catalyst loading up to $1 g L^{-1}$, beyond that the slopes are nearly equal. For a constant time of 15 min irradiation, the decolourisation efficiency exhibits a sharp increase up to a catalyst loading of $1 g L^{-1}$ and then it decreases with further increase in catalyst loading [Fig. 4(b)]. This may be due to increase in the total active surface area with the catalyst dose and availability of more active sites on the surface. At the same time, the increased turbidity of the suspension with high dose of photocatalyst decreased the

Fig. 4. (a) Effect of catalyst loading on degradation of Congo Red. [Dye] = $7.17 \times 10^{-5} M$; (\square) 0.25 g L^{-1} , (\circ) 0.50 g L^{-1} , (Δ) 1.00 g L^{-1} , (\star) 1.50 g L^{-1} , (∇) 2.00 g L^{-1} . (b) Degradation as a function of catalyst loading for irradiation of 15 min.

penetration of light and photoactivated volume of the suspension. Hence an optimum catalyst dose of 1 g L^{-1} was selected for further studies.

Effect of dye concentration :

The effect of initial dye concentration on the photodegradation was investigated by varying the dye concentration from $7.17 \times 10^{-6} M$ to $2.87 \times 10^{-4} M$ at constant catalyst dose (Fig. 5). The percent degradation gradually decreased with increase in initial dye concentration. As the dye concentration increases, the equilibrium adsorption of dye molecules on the active sites of the catalyst surface increases, but competitive adsorption

Fig. 5. Effect of dye concentration on degradation of Congo Red. [Ag-ZnO] = 1.0 g L^{-1} ; (\square) $7.17 \times 10^{-6} M$, (\circ) $1.43 \times 10^{-5} M$, (Δ) $2.87 \times 10^{-5} M$, (\star) $7.17 \times 10^{-5} M$, (∇) $1.43 \times 10^{-4} M$, (\diamond) $2.87 \times 10^{-4} M$.

of OH^- on the same sites decreases. Hence, the generation of relative number of OH^* on the surface of the catalyst decreases. On the other hand, with increase in dye concentration the path length of photons entering the solution decreases, which results in lower adsorption of photons on the catalyst surface, and consequent decrease in degradation efficiency²¹.

Effect of pH :

Industries releases effluents with different pH values and it is the major factor influencing the rate of the photocatalytic process. Hence, the effect of pH on the decolourisation efficiency was studied at various pH values ranging from 2 to 12 for constant dye concentration and catalyst loading (Fig. 6). It was observed that the decolourisation efficiency was increased in the acidic range and is high at natural pH of the dye solution (6.95) and then it is decreased in the alkaline range. The pH of the solution dictates the charge on the particle surface. The zero point charge for ZnO is 9.0 and ZnO surface is positively charged below pH 9.0 and negatively charged above pH 9.0 due to adsorbed OH^- ions. The decrease in degradation at higher pH value may be due to repulsion between negatively charged dye molecules and catalyst surface.

Kinetic analysis :

The kinetics of dye degradation has been described

Fig. 6. Effect of initial pH of dye solution on degradation of Congo Red. [Congo Red] = $7.17 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Ag-ZnO] = 1.0 g L^{-1} , pH values are (□) 2.15, (○) 4.35, (Δ) 6.95, (☆) 9.31, (∇) 11.70.

well by the Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetic model²² :

$$r = \frac{dC}{dt} = \frac{kKC}{1 + KC}$$

where r is rate of dye degradation. As KC is very small compared to unity, neglecting KC in the denominator and integrating with respect to time t , simplifies the above equation to pseudo-first order kinetic equation,

$$\ln(C_0/C) = kKt = k_{app} t$$

C_0 is initial concentration of dye, C is the concentration of dye at time t , k is the rate constant and K is the adsorption coefficient of the dye onto the photocatalyst surface.

The kinetic plots for the degradation of Congo Red under optimal catalyst dose of ZnO and Ag-ZnO are shown in Fig. 7. The apparent rate constants were calculated from the slope of the linear plot between $\ln(C_0/C)$ versus t by regression analysis. The values were found to be 0.0145 and 0.0727 min^{-1} for degradation of Congo Red on ZnO and Ag-ZnO, respectively.

Mechanism of photocatalytic degradation :

The photocatalytic degradation of a dye in the presence of semiconductor is initiated by the photoexcitation of the semiconductor, followed by the formation of electron-hole pair. Part of these photogenerated carriers recombine in the bulk of the semiconductor, while the rest migrate to the surface of the catalyst, where the holes act

Fig. 7. Kinetic plots for degradation of Congo Red on (a) ZnO and (b) 1% Ag-ZnO. [Congo Red] = $7.17 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Catalyst] = 1 g L^{-1} .

as powerful oxidants and the electrons as powerful reductants and initiate a wide range of redox reactions. The high oxidative potential of the hole causes the direct oxidation of the dye to reactive intermediates. Another reactive intermediate responsible for the degradation is hydroxyl radical formed by the decomposition of water or by reaction of hole with OH^- . The hydroxyl radical is an extremely strong non-selective oxidant which leads to partial or complete mineralization of the dye (Fig. 8)²³. The mechanism of photo degradation can be explained as follows.

Alternately, the electron in the conduction band can be picked up by the adsorbed dye molecules, leading to the formation of the dye radical anion, which is subsequently degraded (Fig. 8b). The enhanced photocatalytic activity by Ag addition may be explained by its ability to trap electrons and this process reduces the recombination of charges and favours the oxidation of the substrate¹⁶. It was observed that the catalyst was slightly darkened during the irradiation due to reduction of silver ions to me-

Fig. 8. Possible mechanism for degradation of Congo Red initiated by (a) e^-_{aq} and (b) OH^- .

tallic silver. Higher concentrations of silver impregnation could be unfavourable to photocatalytic efficiency. It is assumed that silver impregnation below optimum value acts as electron-hole separation center²⁴, whereas above optimum value it can act as charge carrier recombination center²⁵.

Conclusions

Impregnation of ZnO with silver drastically enhanced

the photocatalytic activity. The optimum concentration of silver for impregnation by this method was found to be 1 atom%. Calcination of the samples at higher temperature has a negative impact on photocatalytic activity. The characterization of samples by XRD indicated that impregnation with silver did not change the crystal structure of ZnO. The percentage degradation of Congo Red increased with catalyst dose up to an optimum loading. Further increase in catalyst dose showed a little effect. The pho-

photocatalytic degradation of Congo Red followed pseudo-first order kinetics.

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